

Synoptic Drivers and Moisture Sources of Snowfall in Coastal Victoria Land, Antarctica

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Key Points:

- We combine Self-Organizing Map (SOM) analysis with a moisture source diagnostic to study precipitation dynamics of coastal Victoria Land (VL)
- The moisture sources of snowfall in VL are in the Southern Ocean, with local sources in the Ross Sea during summer when sea ice is reduced
- VL has a strong distinction in moisture sources: the north receives moisture dominantly from the west and the south from the east

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Citation:

Hofsteenge, M. G., Cullen, N. J., Sodemann, H., & Katurji, M. (2025). Synoptic drivers and moisture sources of snowfall in coastal Victoria Land, Antarctica. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres*, 130, e2024JD042021. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2024JD042021>

Received 1 AUG 2024
Accepted 7 FEB 2025

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Abstract Snowfall is an important component of the mass balance of ice sheets and glaciers in Antarctica. In coastal Victoria Land (VL), changes to snowfall can impact ice masses, landscapes, and coastal ecosystems. Coastal VL is characterized by strong gradients in snowfall rates between the polar desert of the McMurdo Dry Valleys and the high accumulation in northern VL. Extreme precipitation events significantly contribute to total precipitation, with the largest contribution in the Terra Nova Bay area. We present a comprehensive analysis of snowfall dynamics in this region, using a Lagrangian moisture source diagnostic to study moisture sources and Self-Organizing Maps (SOM) to link these to different synoptic weather types. The moisture for snowfall in VL originates from the Southern Ocean, with more local sources in the Ross Sea embayment in summer when sea ice is reduced. We show a strong division in moisture sources between northern and southern VL, with the north receiving precipitation from moisture sources to the west and southern VL from the east. Precipitation in northern VL results from meridional transport of marine air from lower latitudes, while precipitation in southern VL is related to cyclonic disturbances in the Ross Sea that bring moisture from the east. Extreme precipitation in northern VL occurs during blocking highs that intensify meridional transport. Such intrusions of marine air, sometimes in the form of atmospheric rivers, do not impact the more isolated western Ross Ice Shelf and southern VL further in the Ross Sea embayment.

Plain Language Summary Snowfall is important for the mass balance of glaciers and ice sheets and ecosystems in coastal Victoria Land (VL). The region has large differences in snowfall rates, from the driest conditions in the McMurdo Dry Valleys to the highest snowfall rates in northern VL. We study the sources of moisture for snowfall in this region and the dominant weather patterns that transport the moisture. We find that the moisture for snowfall in VL comes primarily from the Southern Ocean, especially south of Australia and New Zealand. In summer, there is an increased role of nearby moisture sources because of openings in the sea ice in the Ross Sea. We find a clear separation between northern VL that has moisture sources to the west, and southern VL that has moisture sources to the east. In northern VL, precipitation comes from marine air from lower latitudes, while in southern VL, it is caused by cyclones in the Ross Sea bringing moisture from the east. Extreme precipitation in northern VL occurs during persistent high-pressure systems that increase the transport of warm and marine air from lower latitudes to Antarctica. Such intrusions often do not reach southern VL, which is deeper in the Ross Sea embayment.

1. Introduction

Snowfall is the main source of the Antarctic surface mass balance and therefore plays a key role in determining global sea level rise. Antarctic precipitation is projected to increase with global warming and could partly offset the global sea level rise from Antarctic mass loss (Palermé et al., 2017). The precise impact of changes in Antarctic snowfall on sea level rise remains unclear, as it could potentially increase ice discharge, thereby contributing to sea level rise (Winkelmann et al., 2012).

Coastal Victoria Land (VL) stretches from the Ross Ice Shelf in the south to Cape Adare in the north, where the Trans-Antarctic Mountains form a transition zone between the Eastern Antarctic Ice Sheet and the Ross Sea (Figure 2a). The region has outlet glaciers from the Antarctic Ice Sheet and ice shelves, ice-free areas of which the largest are the McMurdo Dry Valleys (MDV) and glacier and snow-covered mountains in northern VL. In the MDV, snowfall impacts the duration of the ablation season and drives inter-annual variability in melt and stream flow through its impact on albedo and other energy exchanges (Fountain et al., 1999; Hoffman et al., 2008; Hofsteenge et al., 2023). Changes in snowfall in the MDV can therefore impact hydrological and ecological

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connectivity. Also in other ice-free regions in coastal VL, terrestrial ecosystems are mostly limited by the availability of liquid water through snow and ice melt (Barrett et al., 2006). Thus, understanding the drivers behind snowfall is essential for predicting changes in the ice masses, landscapes, and ecosystems of coastal VL.

Variability and changes in Antarctic snowfall are controlled by both thermodynamic and dynamic processes. The thermodynamic processes refer to changes in atmospheric moisture, such as the increase in moisture content with air temperature through the Clausius-Clapeyron relationship (Nicola et al., 2023). Other thermodynamic processes include the evaporative moisture sources of snowfall (Gao et al., 2024; Sodemann & Stohl, 2009). Changes in sea ice cover can impact such evaporative sources and resulting Antarctic snowfall (H. Wang et al., 2020). In the Arctic, the expected increase in snowfall is likely due to an increase in local evaporation through sea ice retreat (Bintanja & Selten, 2014).

Dynamic processes involve atmospheric circulation ranging from meso to synoptic through to the large scale. Marine air is transported from lower latitudes to Antarctica through strong meridional transport on planetary waves. During blocking conditions, the circumpolar jet is highly amplified and so-called atmospheric rivers (ARs) can bring extreme amounts of moisture to Antarctica (Nash et al., 2018). ARs cause extreme precipitation in East Antarctica (Gorodetskaya et al., 2014; Wille et al., 2021) and impact surface melt and ice shelf stability on the Antarctic Peninsula (Gorodetskaya et al., 2023) and West Antarctica (Wille et al., 2019). Extreme precipitation events are dominant in explaining inter-annual variability in Antarctic precipitation, especially in coastal regions (Turner et al., 2019).

The importance of extreme precipitation to total precipitation is especially high on the Ross Ice Shelf and in the Terra Nova Bay area (Turner et al., 2019). While ARs are the main cause of extreme precipitation in many coastal areas of Antarctica, ARs do not reach far into the Ross Sea embayment, which makes this region the one with the lowest AR frequency (Wille et al., 2021). Instead, synoptic-cyclones that travel in circumpolar westerly winds commonly track into the Ross Sea and have been linked to snowfall variability at two ice core sites in the Ross Sea region (Sinclair et al., 2010). Synoptic-scale cyclones occur frequently in the Amundsen Sea and their maximum occurrence shifts to the Ross Sea in winter, being significant contributors to precipitation (Papritz et al., 2014). The Ross Sea region, where radiatively cooled air from the Antarctic Plateau flows off the continent as katabatic winds, is also a hotspot for mesocyclone and boundary layer front development that can lead to convective precipitation (Bove & Paolo, 2009; Carrasco et al., 2003).

This study aims to improve understanding of the synoptic circulation patterns and moisture origins of precipitation in coastal VL. Such insights will support efforts to predict potential shifts in snowfall distribution, which will inevitably have consequences for ice shelves, glaciers, and coastal ecosystems in the region. We expect contrasts between the northern regions, which are exposed to the Southern Ocean weather systems, and the southern VL, which are more isolated and deeper in the Ross Sea embayment. We present a comprehensive analysis of snowfall dynamics of this region with a climatology of the synoptic drivers of snowfall using Self-Organizing Maps and the moisture pathways and evaporative sources of snowfall using a Lagrangian approach.

2. Data and Methods

2.1. ERA5 Precipitation and Extreme Precipitation Definition

We use the European Center for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF's) ERA5 reanalysis product to study precipitation patterns and synoptic weather types over 44 years from 1979 to 2023. The ERA5 precipitation and geopotential height fields are retrieved on a $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ horizontal grid. Reanalysis products generally underestimate snow over the Antarctic plateau as they do not include clear sky precipitation and underestimate the effect of topography because of their limited spatial resolution. ERA5 performs better compared to its predecessor ERA-interim, likely because of the application of mixed-phase clouds that improves the cloud and precipitation in the model (Ning et al., 2024). Comparison of different reanalysis products over Antarctica shows that ERA5 is best at representing accumulation (Gossart et al., 2019; Ning et al., 2024).

To define extreme precipitation in ERA5, we use the 95th percentile level as a threshold. First, a precipitation day is defined as a day receiving a minimum of 0.02 mm d^{-1} , following Turner et al. (2019). Then, the 95th percentile is determined using data from all identified precipitation days. Daily precipitation that is equal to or exceeds the 95th percentile is considered extreme precipitation.

2.2. Synoptic Weather Typing

We investigate the atmospheric circulation patterns leading to precipitation with Self-Organizing Map (SOM) analysis, applied to ERA5 850 hPa geopotential height over a region covering the Ross Sea (between 150°E and 110°W and 90°S and 50°S). Using SOM analysis on gridded atmospheric pressure and/or wind fields has proven to be successful (Sheridan & Lee, 2011) and has previously been used to study wind regimes in the Ross Sea region (Katurji et al., 2019; Seefeldt & Cassano, 2012). The 850 hPa level is chosen to represent the near-surface atmospheric circulation, while being less affected by topography compared with mean sea-level pressure. We use 44 years of daily averages of geopotential height to construct the SOM. First, spatial anomalies of 850 hPa geopotential height are calculated by subtracting at each time the domain average from each grid cell. Spatial anomalies are used to train the SOM to retain the exact geopotential height gradient which can explain moisture transport. We use the MiniSom (Vettigli, 2018) algorithm to perform the SOM training with the following parameters: a matrix of 3×4 , 5000 training iterations, a sigma of 1 and a learning rate of 0.01. Among the configurations tested, this set of parameters consistently delivered the most stable outcomes across multiple executions of MiniSom. A 3×4 matrix was chosen because it most effectively balances clarity in pattern interpretation while still capturing sufficient variability.

2.3. Lagrangian Backward Trajectories

To study the moisture transport pathways and source regions of precipitation in coastal VL, we apply the Lagrangian moisture source and transport diagnostic developed by Sodemann et al. (2008). This method maps moisture source regions by analyzing the specific humidity changes along Lagrangian backward trajectories arriving in a target area. We use LAGRANTO (Sprenger & Wernli, 2015) to calculate backward trajectories on the full spatial and vertical resolution of ERA5 (137 vertical model levels) for coastal VL (see below). LAGRANTO uses the three-dimensional kinematic wind fields on the ERA5 model levels to calculate three-dimensional trajectories. Because of the high data storage requirements of ERA5, the Lagrangian analysis is focused on a subset of the study period between 2016 and 2023. This might introduce a bias toward low Antarctic sea ice conditions as a regime shift took place from 2016 (Himmich et al., 2024). Despite this, our combined method still reveals valuable links between synoptic circulation patterns and moisture sources and seasonality in moisture sources due to sea ice presence. Differences in atmospheric circulation between this sub-period and the full SOM analysis are addressed in Section 3.5. Furthermore, we use 3-hourly input data instead of the 1-hourly resolution that are available from ERA5. Even at a down-sampled temporal resolution, ERA5 performs better compared to the previous ERA-interim because of improvements in the forecasting model, observations, and assimilation system (Hoffmann et al., 2019).

Trajectories are released over a regular grid covering coastal VL (box in Figure 1a, between 159°E–171.3°E and 79°S–71.6°S), with a spacing of 20×20 km and only released over land points. The trajectories are released from the surface up to 500 hPa, with fixed intervals of 30 hPa. This results in 5819 10-day backward trajectories computed per 3-hr time step over the period between 2016 and 2023. Trajectory analysis was previously used to detect Antarctic precipitation moisture sources using 5-day trajectories (Reijmer et al., 2002), but Sodemann and Stohl (2009) found that these were too short and found that a computation time of 10 days was acceptable, even if longer trajectories led to a further increase in the precipitation fraction that could be attributed to a source region.

2.4. Moisture Source Attribution Diagnostic WaterSip

The WaterSip software tool uses the moisture source diagnostic as described in Sodemann et al. (2008). Trajectories were selected as precipitating in the arrival location when specific humidity decreased at least 0.1 g kg^{-1} over a 3 hr time step, and relative humidity was at least 75% at the last time step. While the 75% threshold is lower than the 80% employed by Sodemann et al. (2008), it is justified in the context of Antarctica, where ice phase clouds play a more significant role (Sodemann & Stohl, 2009). With these criteria about 4.6 million trajectories were selected as precipitating within the study period and used to map the moisture sources and transport during precipitation.

A trajectory point is identified as a moisture uptake location when the traced air parcel experiences an increase in specific humidity that is larger than Δq while located within the boundary layer (Sodemann et al., 2008). The boundary layer criterion assumes that moisture uptake can be directly related to evaporation sources at the surface when the parcel is within the boundary layer, while the so-called free-troposphere uptakes are identified

Figure 1. Evaluation of WaterSip. Annual (a) Lagrangian precipitation estimate (mm) and (b) ERA5 precipitation (mm) over target region. (c) Monthly boxplots of the fraction of precipitation that could be attributed to an uptake in the boundary layer using WaterSip. All are given for the period 2016–2023.

otherwise. A Δq of $0.05 \text{ g kg}^{-1} 3 \text{ h}^{-1}$ is used as in Sodemann and Stohl (2009), but is adjusted for the shorter time-step of 3 hr instead of 6 hr. As in previous studies, we use a boundary layer height factor of 1.5 to separate between events clearly related to evaporation below and free-troposphere uptakes.

The total domain precipitation estimate of WaterSip correlates very well with total domain precipitation in ERA5 (R^2 of 0.90) but is on average 30% smaller. This underestimation is due to the simplification in how precipitation is estimated in WaterSip, which relies on a threshold for humidity decrease in the final time step, thereby excluding small precipitation events, and neglects cloud microphysical processes (Sodemann et al., 2008). Still, to study the moisture sources of precipitation, it is more relevant that the spatial and temporal variability in precipitation is captured rather than the actual amounts, as previously argued by Sodemann and Zubler (2010). Spatial patterns in the WaterSip precipitation estimate are very similar to the ERA5 precipitation (Figures 1a and 1b).

A limitation of the Lagrangian diagnostic is that not all precipitation can be attributed to an evaporative source. In this study, we can attribute on average 57% of the precipitation to moisture uptake in the boundary layer, and 37%

Figure 2. ERA5 (a) surface orography (m), (b) annual precipitation (mm), and (c) contribution of extreme precipitation (≥ 95 th percentile) to the total precipitation (%) between 1979 and 2023. The dashed box shows the coastal Victoria Land target region used for the Lagrangian moisture source analysis.

Figure 3. Seasonal mean moisture sources: Moisture uptake contribution to precipitation over coastal Victoria Land (black dashed box) in mm for (a) summer, (b) autumn, (c) winter, and (d) spring. The yellow contour indicates the mean sea ice extent for the season between 2016 and 2023.

in the free troposphere. The boundary-layer fraction however shows some seasonality (Figure 1c), with increased attribution in winter (up to 68% in August) and decreased attribution in summer (down to 47% in December). Previous studies using the WaterSip diagnostic tool have found similar attribution factors: for example, 48% for the dry region of north-east Greenland (Schuster et al., 2021), 66% for Greenland winter precipitation (Sodemann et al., 2008), and 50% for the European Alps (Sodemann & Zubler, 2010).

3. Results

3.1. Ross Sea Precipitation and Extreme Precipitation Contribution

Figure 2a shows the spatial distribution of annual mean precipitation over the Ross Sea region during 1979–2023. The highest precipitation rates occur in front of the coast of northern VL and northern Marie Byrd Land, where air masses rapidly rise when reaching the Antarctic topography. Similar orographic effects on precipitation are visible along the Trans-Antarctic Mountain Range. The driest region within the focus area is the MDV, which resides in the precipitation shadow of the Trans-Antarctic Mountains. This region has annual precipitation values below 100 mm, in contrast to the southern side of the Trans-Antarctic Mountains which reach up to ~400 mm per year. Note that the orographic precipitation patterns are likely more complex in reality because of the limited spatial resolution of ERA5.

Extreme precipitation is defined as days when precipitation is above the 95th percentile. The absolute threshold is therefore spatially variable in the domain, with the 95th percentile around 10 mm d^{-1} south of the Trans-Antarctic Mountains, around 2 mm d^{-1} in the MDV and 6 mm d^{-1} in Terra Nova Bay (not shown). The contribution of extreme precipitation to total precipitation is the largest on the Ross Ice Shelf and in the coastal areas, especially in the Terra Nova Bay area (more than 55%, Figure 2b). These locations of maximum extreme precipitation contribution agree with an Antarctic-wide study on extreme precipitation events using the RACMO2 data (Turner et al., 2019). The authors explained that the strong katabatic winds in these regions hinder the penetration of maritime airmasses, making the infrequent extreme precipitation events more impactful.

3.2. Seasonality in Moisture Sources

The seasonality of moisture uptake regions for precipitation in coastal VL is shown in Figure 3, based on the Lagrangian trajectory analysis with WaterSip between 2016 and 2023. In all seasons, evaporation in the Southern

Ocean around Tasmania and New Zealand is an important source of moisture for precipitation, as well as some areas in the Amundsen and Bellinghousen Sea. Between February and March, the Antarctic sea ice is at its minimum, and local evaporation from open water in the Ross Sea embayment becomes an important moisture source for precipitation over VL. The local uptake is reduced in winter and spring when sea ice covers most of the Ross Sea embayment, apart from open areas in the Ross Sea and Terra Nova Bay polynyas. Because of the low specific humidity in winter, effective evaporation is still possible from leads and polynyas in the sea ice (Appendix A, Figure A1).

Local uptake is also visible southeast of the Ross Ice Shelf and on the western Ross Ice Shelf. In summer, such continental recycling of moisture could occur over the Ross Ice Shelf when solar radiation is available for sublimation/evaporation. This was found to be a small (3%) contributor to summer Antarctic precipitation using a water tagging model study (Gao et al., 2024). These regions of local moisture uptake on the continent agree with the highest evaporation rates in ERA5 (Figure A1), which was also found by Naakka et al. (2021) and explained as being due to dominant dry air advection from the higher elevation areas that enables evaporation. In this study, the contribution of moisture uptake over land varies between 6% in autumn and 16% in summer. Note that this fraction depends on the trajectory length, as longer trajectories likely detect a larger oceanic fraction.

The stronger contribution of local moisture sources in summer agrees with previous findings by Sodemann and Stohl (2009) using the same moisture source diagnostic on ERA-40 reanalysis over the entire Antarctic continent. Local moisture sources in summer and distant moisture sources in winter can be explained by seasonality in sea ice cover. However, a recent study by Gao et al. (2024) using a water tagging atmospheric circulation model found that moisture source regions of Antarctic precipitation were most poleward in autumn and winter and most equatorward in summer. Although minimal sea ice extent during DJF would suggest more poleward moisture sources, Gao et al. (2024) hypothesize that the equatorward shift in moisture sources is due to weaker westerlies caused by smaller meridional thermal gradients during DJF.

3.3. Spatial Variability in Moisture Sources

The moisture sources shown in Figure 3 show the uptake regions for all precipitation within the VL target area; however, the dominant moisture source regions might spatially differ within VL. Figure 4 therefore shows the mean source latitude and relative source longitude over VL. Precipitation at higher elevations generally has moisture sources further north (Figure 4a) compared with lower elevation sites. This agrees with previous studies and can be explained with the moist isentropic framework: poleward moisture transport largely follows surfaces of constant moist entropy (Gao et al., 2024; Sodemann & Stohl, 2009; Stohl & Sodemann, 2010). Figures 4c and 4d show the anomalies in source longitude and latitude for days considered as extreme precipitation days, which are based on 44-year of ERA5 precipitation data, as described in Section 2.1. During extreme precipitation days, the source latitude tends to be further north for most of the domain (Figure 4c). Only for some regions in the Terra Nova Bay area and south of the Trans-Antarctic Mountains, is the source latitude slightly further south or not different during extreme precipitation.

The VL region is particularly interesting when looking at the relative source longitude (Figure 4b), which shows the longitude of the moisture source relative to the longitude of the precipitation location. There seems to be a clear distinction between northern VL having a predominantly western moisture source region, and southern VL having a predominantly eastern moisture source region. On average, the “inflection point” between sources to the west or the east lies in the Terra Nova Bay area. For the MDV, moisture for precipitation comes, on average, from the east. However, further south of the Trans-Antarctic Mountains, the eastern displacement is the largest, with source longitudes up to 100° to the east. This distinct pattern is also visible in the moisture sources estimated by Gao et al. (2024), who observed that while Antarctic precipitation typically comes from the west, the region between the South Pole and Terra Nova Bay is an exception, with moisture originating from the east.

For extreme precipitation in northern VL, moisture sources shift on average eastward (Figure 4d). For much of the central VL and around Ross Island and on the western Ross Ice Shelf, the moisture sources of extreme precipitation are westward compared with normal precipitation. In the following sections, we combine the moisture source analysis with SOM analysis to explain the synoptic drivers of spatial variability in moisture sources found in Figure 4.

Figure 4. (a) Mean source latitude and (b) relative source longitude of moisture uptake regions contributing to precipitation in coastal Victoria Land (dashed black box) between 2016 and 2023. (c) and (d) show the anomalies in source latitude (c) and longitude (d) for extreme precipitation days (see definition in Section 2.1).

3.4. Synoptic Climatology and Precipitation in Ross Sea Region

The 12 SOM nodes in Figure 5 represent the dominant patterns in the near-surface atmospheric circulation based on daily spatial geopotential height anomalies at 850 hPa. The nodes characterize the basic features of the synoptic conditions between 1979 and 2023. Note that the pressure perturbations are spatially more extended and smoother than typical synoptic pressure systems because of the averaging of multiple patterns into one node. The frequency of the days that fall within each cluster during the period is given as a percentage above each node.

The SOM nodes in Figure 5 show the variability in the location of low-pressure systems in the Ross Sea region and the strength of circumpolar westerlies. Nodes that occur during the positive phase of the Southern Annular Mode (SAM) are located in the lower-left corner of the SOM. Specifically, Nodes 5, 9, and 10 have a significant positive correlation with the SAM index (not shown). In contrast, nodes that occur during the negative phase of SAM are in the upper right corner, with Nodes 3, 4, and 8 having significant negative correlations with the SAM index (not shown). During the positive phase of SAM, the pressure over Antarctica is lower and westerly winds are intensified and shifted poleward. During the negative phase, there is higher pressure over Antarctica and weakened and northward displaced westerlies.

This semi-permanent low-pressure system in the Ross Sea and Amundsen Sea is known as the climatological Amundsen Sea Low (ASL). When the low-pressure system is positioned in the Ross Sea (e.g., Nodes 5–7), it causes southerly surface winds over the western Ross Ice Shelf (Seefeldt & Cassano, 2012), foehn winds in the MDV (Hofsteenge et al., 2022; Speirs et al., 2010), and precipitation on the east to south-east side of the Trans-Antarctic Mountains (Nodes 5–7 in Figure 7). The most extreme precipitation in southern VL and the MDV occurs during Node 7 (Figures 7 and 8), when the low-pressure system is centered in the Ross Sea region. In addition to the spatial anomalies that are used for SOM clustering, we show for each SOM node the climatological anomalies (relative to 1979–2023 climatology) in Figure 6. These provide a clearer understanding of precipitation extremes, and show anomalously low pressure during Node 7. This node also contributes to extreme precipitation in the Terra Nova Bay area (Figure 8). When the low-pressure system is positioned further west, as seen in Node 3, extreme precipitation is largest in the Terra Nova Bay. This westward position of the low is likely a precursor to Node 7.

The highest total and extreme precipitation rates in northern VL occur during Node 1, when the low is positioned north of VL and high pressure extends into the eastern Ross Sea (Figures 5 and 6). This region frequently experiences persistent high-pressure systems (e.g., blocking highs), which are related to extreme precipitation in East Antarctica (S. Wang et al., 2024). The high- and low-pressure anomaly couplet for Node 1 in Figure 6 signals the presence of such a blocking high during these extreme precipitation events. Similar pressure anomaly couplets

Figure 5. Self-Organizing Map (SOM) showing a 3 by 4 matrix of geopotential height distributions over the Ross Sea region based on ERA5 for 1979–2023. Red and blue colors indicate positive and negative spatial anomalies in the 850 hPa geopotential height, calculated as described in Section 2.2. In the brackets above each subplot the percentage occurrence of the specific SOM node is shown.

Figure 6. Climatological 850 hPa geopotential height anomaly for each of the SOM nodes in Figure 5. The climatological anomaly is calculated by subtracting the long-term mean (1979–2023).

Figure 7. Annual precipitation in mm corresponding to each of the SOM nodes given in Figure 5 based on ERA5 for 1979–2023. Areas are dotted if that node has the largest amount of extreme precipitation days (see definition in Section 2.1).

have been found as common drivers of AR precipitation in East Antarctica (Baiman et al., 2023; Wille et al., 2024). Indeed, Node 1 is associated with ARs occurring in the Ross Sea that occasionally make landfall in northern VL (Figure B1, Appendix B). During the neighboring Node 5, which shows an eastward displacement of the pattern in Node 1, precipitation is most extreme in the eastern Ross Sea region and over the Ross Ice Shelf.

Seasonal precipitation patterns are influenced by shifts in moisture sources and atmospheric circulation patterns throughout the year. The presence of sea ice contributes to the seasonality of moisture sources, as discussed in Section 3.2. Figure 9 shows the seasonality in SOM node frequency. It can be seen from Figure 9 that seasonality in precipitation in the sub-regions agrees with seasonality in the SOM nodes that bring most precipitation to this region (Figure 7). In Northern VL, precipitation rates peak in summer (Figure 9b), coinciding with the increased frequency of Node 1 (Figure 9a), which contributes the most extreme precipitation to the area (Figure 7). In contrast, Southern VL experiences its highest precipitation during autumn and spring, aligning with a greater occurrence of Node 5 during these months (Figure 9). This seasonal variability in precipitation is closely tied to

Figure 8. Annual mean precipitation per SOM node in each sub-region of VL in (e), with contribution from extreme precipitation hatched and error bars showing standard deviation between the years. Regions show McMurdo Dry Valleys (MDV), Southern Victoria Land (SVL), Terra Nova Bay area (TNB), and Northern Victoria Land (NVL).

the synoptic conditions represented by the SOM nodes, highlighting the strong link between atmospheric circulation and regional moisture dynamics.

3.5. Moisture Uptake and Transport During SOM Nodes

To further study the moisture pathways for the weather types, we combine the SOM analysis with the moisture source attribution analysis. For each SOM node (Figure 5), Figure 10 shows the total moisture transport in mm, which is obtained as the composite of the vertical integral of specific humidity along precipitating backward trajectories. The black contours indicate the region where some moisture uptake took place (dashed line) and where moisture uptake was the strongest (solid lines). Note that there are minor discrepancies in the percentages of node occurrences when compared with Figure 5, since a shorter period between 2016 and 2023 is used in the moisture source analysis. The differences in node occurrences lie in a decrease in occurrence in Nodes 3, 8, and 12 and an increase in occurrence in Nodes 9 and 10, reflecting a change to the predominantly positive phase of SAM in recent years.

Figure 9. (a) Monthly mean frequency of SOM nodes, with shaded regions indicating the standard deviation. (b) Monthly mean ERA5 precipitation for each sub-region of coastal VL.

Figure 10. Moisture transport (mm) and uptake regions per SOM node of Figure 5 between 2016 and 2023. Blue shading shows per node the moisture transport as total water vapor traced to precipitation events in coastal Victoria Land (gray box) using Lagrangian backward trajectories. Moisture uptake regions are indicated with black contours (total moisture uptake of 0.1 mm with dashed contours and 0.3 mm with solid contours).

The input of moisture to VL is largest when meridional flow brings warm and moist air from lower latitudes to Antarctica. This is most evident from Node 1 (Figure 10), which shows the largest moisture transport and strong contribution of moisture uptake from the seas around Australia and New Zealand. Such conditions of meridional flow can occur during periods of weakened circumpolar westerlies when the planetary waves are amplified. For Node 1, warm and humid air is transported on the western flank of the blocking high from the seas around New Zealand and Tasmania to the Ross Sea region (Figure 6). In such cases, most of the precipitation occurs when the moist air flow is lifted by the sloping topography at the Antarctic coast, bringing precipitation to higher-elevation sites in northern VL, while being dried out before reaching more southern latitudes (Figure 7). The strong meridional moisture transport during Node 1 explains why the moisture for extreme precipitation in northern VL has an origin further north than usual as was found in Figure 4.

The highest and most extreme precipitation in southern VL and the MDV occurs with synoptic cyclones in the Ross Sea (Nodes 5–7), that transport moisture originating from the Southern Ocean off the coast of Marie Byrd Land to the Ross Sea region (Figure 10). This explains the source longitude to the east, as described in Section 3.3. When the cyclone is positioned further east in the Ross Sea, such as Node 11, the air masses are less moist since a lot of the moisture is lost when the air travels over Marie Byrd Land. Moisture sources are most westward during the positive phase of SAM when westerlies are the strongest. This is reflected in the moisture source and transport pathways for Nodes 5, 9, and 10 in Figure 10.

4. Discussion

Considering the significant impact of extreme precipitation on coastal Antarctica (Turner et al., 2019), recent research has focused on exploring the synoptic drivers behind extreme precipitation events (Swetha Chittella et al., 2022). Strong marine air intrusions from lower latitudes are often responsible for extreme precipitation, sometimes in the form of atmospheric rivers (Gorodetskaya et al., 2014; Terpstra et al., 2021; Wille et al., 2021). Our study confirms the importance of such processes in delivering precipitation and extreme precipitation to northern VL. However, we also show that in many cases, these intrusions do not extend to the more isolated

regions within the Ross Sea embayment. Instead, precipitation on the Ross Ice Shelf and southern VL is related to synoptic cyclones in the Ross Sea.

The global domain of reanalysis products, such as ERA5, makes them useful data sets for tracing moisture pathways, even back to far-away sources. However, some smaller-scale processes that are relevant for precipitation are not accounted for, such as the formation of mesocyclones. Carrasco et al. (2003) found at Ross Island that the months with the highest occurrence of mesoscale cyclones also had the highest amounts of precipitation. Other mesoscale processes include convective precipitation related to boundary-layer fronts from strong katabatic surges (Bove & Paolo, 2009). Therefore, future research should use higher-resolution regional climate models to explore mesoscale interactions related to precipitation and moisture uptake, particularly concerning katabatic winds, mesocyclones, and moisture uptake in coastal polynyas in the Ross Sea region.

While this study focused on the synoptic drivers and moisture sources for precipitation, it is important to note that sublimation of precipitation also contributes to shaping the precipitation regime of VL. Deuterium excess values are exceptionally low in the McMurdo Dry Valleys because of strong sublimation of snowfall (Hu et al., 2022), likely due to the dominant foehn winds in the region (Speirs et al., 2010). The contribution of precipitation in other coastal regions in Antarctica is also diminished because of strong sublimation through persistent foehn or katabatic winds (Grazioli et al., 2017). For example, in a case study in the ice-free region of the Vestfold Hills, an atmospheric river made landfall but snowfall was limited because of strong sublimation due to a foehn effect (Gehring et al., 2022).

The main limitation of the Lagrangian moisture source attribution with WaterSip is that not all precipitation can be linked to an evaporative source, which is reflected by the attribution factor (Figure 1c). This introduces uncertainty in the contribution of close versus far-away moisture sources. In our study, we observe a different seasonal pattern in the source latitude of precipitation compared with the recent findings of Gao et al. (2024). They found that moisture sources were most poleward in autumn and winter and most equatorward in summer. In contrast, we find that during summer, when sea ice cover is reduced, moisture sources tend to be more local. This observation aligns with the results of Sodemann and Stohl (2009) and Noone and Simmonds (2002). The discrepancies with the study by Gao et al. (2024) may stem from differences in the moisture tracking model and grid resolution that are used. According to Gao et al. (2024), equatorward sources contribute more in summer due to stronger meridional moisture transport, which aligns with our findings of the seasonality in Node 1, associated with the strongest meridional moisture transport (Figure 9a). These findings show that seasonality in moisture sources result from a balance between the variability in evaporation and the atmospheric circulation patterns that transport moisture.

The spatial differences in synoptic drivers and moisture pathways of precipitation that were identified in this study for coastal VL indicate that precipitation could respond in different ways to global warming. Atmospheric river frequency is projected to increase (Espinoza et al., 2018), which will likely impact northern VL the most. More relevant for the Ross Ice Shelf and southern VL are changes to the ASL and cyclone occurrence in the Ross Sea. The ASL has deepened in summer and is expected to deepen further (Raphael et al., 2016). More important for weather in the Ross Sea region is the location rather than its depth, as the ASL shifts eastward when it is deep, thus diminishing its effect on the Ross Sea (Coggins et al., 2014). A western movement of the ASL would increase southward movement of maritime air to the Ross Ice Shelf, although for autumn, the ASL has been shown to have an eastward trend (Coggins & McDonald, 2015).

The strong seasonality in local moisture sources linked to sea ice cover suggests potential significant impacts of Ross Sea sea ice changes on snowfall in VL. Therefore, future research should focus on how changes in sea ice cover affect moisture sources for cloud cover and snowfall, as well as atmospheric circulation patterns. Investigating these aspects in follow-up studies is crucial for our understanding of how snowfall patterns in VL and the ice-free character of the McMurdo Dry Valleys will evolve.

5. Conclusions

In this study, we examined snowfall dynamics of coastal VL utilizing Self-Organizing Maps to establish a climatology of synoptic drivers, while also investigating moisture pathways and evaporative sources through a Lagrangian approach. The combination of methods in this approach allowed us to map the moisture sources and

pathways for different regions within VL and link them with the dominant synoptic weather patterns in the Ross Sea region. Our findings can be summarized as follows:

1. In summer, local moisture sources become more important when less sea ice is present, allowing for more evaporation.
2. The snowfall in coastal VL is marked by a distinct division in moisture source regions: northern VL land has a dominant westerly source region and southern VL has a dominant eastern origin.
3. Northern VL receives most of its precipitation through strong meridional transport, which brings warm and humid air from the Southern Ocean and seas around Australia and New Zealand to the region.
4. Southern VL is sheltered from this meridional transport and receives most of its precipitation through cyclones in the Ross/Amundsen Sea that circulate moisture into the embayment.
5. Extreme precipitation in Northern VL occurs with enhanced meridional moisture flow on the western flank of blocking highs. In southern VL, extreme precipitation is associated with anomalously low pressure in the Ross Sea.

In conclusion, our study underscores the role of the geography of the Ross Sea and synoptic weather patterns in shaping the precipitation dynamics of VL, explaining variations in both snowfall rates and moisture origins. Our study also demonstrates that Lagrangian approaches can be useful to understand how the unique environment of the McMurdo Dry Valleys is formed and maintained. Future studies should focus on the role of mesoscale processes in governing snowfall in VL and the McMurdo Dry Valleys, which are underrepresented in current climate models and reanalysis products, as well as the potential impact of Antarctic sea ice changes on snowfall in coastal regions of Antarctica.

Appendix A: Seasonal Evaporation in ERA5

To illustrate the seasonality in local evaporation and its link to sea ice presence we show in Figure A1 the mean evaporation from ERA5 per season (note negative value reflects evaporation and positive value condensation). Local evaporation is strongly limited in JJA and SON when Antarctic sea ice reaches its largest extent, while in DJF and MAM more local evaporation takes place due to reduced and more open sea ice cover. Some evaporation on land is also visible along the Trans-Antarctic Mountains, strongest in DJF.

Figure A1. Mean ERA5 evaporation in mm for (a) summer, (b) autumn, (c) winter, and (d) spring for 1979–2023. Negative values reflect evaporation/sublimation and positive values condensation/deposition. The yellow contours show the climatological sea ice concentrations of 0.15 (solid contour) and 0.7 (dashed contour).

Appendix B: Atmospheric River Frequency Per Node

Strong meridional moisture transport can occur in the form of Atmospheric Rivers (AR). The frequency of AR's for each of the SOM nodes of Figure 5 is given in Figure B1. The AR's occur most frequently during nodes 1, 5 and 9. AR's mak landfall mostly in East-Antarctica and at the coast of Marie Byrd Land, while they do not reach far into the Ross Sea embayment, the Ross Ice Shelf and southern VL.

Figure B1. Atmospheric River (AR) frequency (%) per SOM nodes of Figure 5. AR frequency is based on hourly detected ARs from Lauer et al. (2023) on integrated water vapor transport in ERA5 (1979–2021).

Data Availability Statement

The complete ERA5 global atmospheric reanalysis data used for synoptic clustering and moisture tracking in the study are available at the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Data Store (CDS) via <https://doi.org/10.24381/cds.143582cf> (Hersbach et al., 2017). The LAGRANTO model code used for the calculation of Lagrangian trajectories is available from www.lagranto.ethz.ch (Sprenger & Wernli, 2015). The WaterSip code used for the moisture source and transport diagnostic is available at <https://git.app.uib.no/GFI-public/watersip>.

Acknowledgments

This research has been supported by the New Zealand Antarctic Science Platform (ANTA1801, program: Projecting Ross Sea Region Ecosystem Changes in a Warming World) and the Royal Society Te Apārangi (Grant RDF-UOC1701). The authors wish to acknowledge the use of New Zealand eScience Infrastructure (NeSI) high-performance computing facilities and support as part of this research (www.nesi.org.nz). The analyses were partly performed using resources provided by Sigma2—the National Infrastructure for High-Performance Computing and Data Storage in Norway. HS acknowledges funding support from the European Research Council H2020 (Grant 773245). The authors would like to thank Chris Weijenborg for his help with data preparation for LAGRANTO runs. Open access publishing facilitated by University of Otago, as part of the Wiley - University of Otago agreement via the Council of Australian University Librarians.

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